

ATMO ACCESS

Access to Atmospheric Research Facilities

Title	First report with feedback from users and statistics on use of the services
Work package n°	10
Deliverable n°	1
Lead beneficiary	NILU
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Deliverable Type	R
Dissemination Level	PU
Estimated delivery date	31 st of October 2023 (M32)
Actual delivery date	23 rd of January 2024
Version	Final
Reviewed by	Sabine Philippin (CNRS), Ariane Dubost (CNRS)
Accepted by	
Comments	

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1. Introduction

This report gives an overview of feedback from users and the statistics on use of the services offered within the Virtual Access (VA) Portal within ATMO-ACCESS for the period from launch in March to June 2023 and until December 2023. The VA Portal (<https://www.atmo-access.eu/virtual-access/#/>) gives access to several online services: the ATMO-ACCESS Homeless Data Portal (<https://homeless-data-portal.nilu.no>), the Time Series Analysis (<https://services.iagos-data.fr/atmo-access/timeseries>) and three different Trajectory and Footprint analysis tools (<https://www.atmo-access.eu/virtual-access/#/footprint-services>). Each of the Research Infrastructures (RIs) in ATMO-ACCESS are responsible for different trajectory and footprint services depending on components and observation platforms, namely Greenhouse Gases (ICOS), Tropospheric vertical gradients (IAGOS) and Aerosol distribution and source analysis (ACTRIS). Access to Massive open online course (MOOC) is scheduled for winter 2024.

Throughout the report, visits refer to when a user enters a webpage or application for the first time or takes any tracked action. 30 minutes after the last action/visit, it is counted as a new visit. The users are counted by individual IP addresses, meaning that there is no distinction between administrators, internal users, or external users. Unique visits refer to visits by unique IP addresses. Requests refer to slightly different things (e.g. data curation, model runs, dataset access) for each service and, if applicable, will be explained in each section.

Feedback is given by user panels, internal feedback, and a general feedback form. User panels consists of a small group of hand-picked people within the RIs that comment on the service in meetings. Internal feedback is feedback picked up on by developers and project leaders over time. The general feedback form is a form available at <https://www.atmo-access.eu/virtual-access-feedback-form/> and have been sent out to users that have agreed to share their e-mail address. Overall, there are few users that provide feedback for each service, despite repeating distribution of feedback forms and invitations to feedback meeting. Accordingly, some of the material for the report is not reflecting all users and the user experience of the services may not be balanced.

2. Virtual Access Portal

The ATMO-ACCESS VA Portal provides access to all online services developed in the ATMO-ACCESS project.

Figure 1: ATMO-ACCESS VA Portal (link: <https://www.atmo-access.eu/virtual-access/>)

When using the ATMO-ACCESS VA Portal, the user is required to log in, as seen in Figure 1. This is to gain statistics for the project, and to collect feedback on the services developed. Figure 2 shows the ATMO-ACCESS VA Portal after login, with buttons giving access to “Data curation of homeless data”, “Trajectory and footprint analysis”, “Tools for analyzing time series” and “Online training service” (not yet available). The “Trajectory and footprint analysis” service includes one tool for each RI, which is Greenhouse Gases (ICOS), Tropospheric vertical gradients (IAGOS) and Aerosol distribution and source analysis (ACTRIS).

ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Access Portal

This portal provides you with access to the new online services developed in the ATMO-ACCESS project. This include access to:

- **Homeless data portal:**
A portal for submission of measurement data from research projects, not associated to any long-term projects/networks nor sustainable data centres. – **New and online**
- **Footprint analysis tool for greenhouse gases, aerosols, reactive trace gases:**
Model tools for interpretation of measurement data both measured at the ground and from aircrafts. You can request model runs to produce data products (e.g footprint, source contributions) for your decided locations, or search and use the already produced products. – **New and online**
- **Time series analysis:**
Identify, utilize and combine data more effectively across RIs and data repositories, including data coverage, collocation of data and visualisation of data. – **New and online**
- **Massive open online course (MOOC)**
Online course on atmospheric observations in European infrastructure scheduled autumn 2023. – **Scheduled autumn 2023**

Data curators of homeless data

Trajectory and footprint analysis

Tools for analysing time series

Online training service

Figure 2: ATMO-ACCESS VA Portal page after login

2.1. Statistics on use of the online services

Statistics on the use of the ATMO-ACCESS online services are tracked in several ways.

- Visits to the whole ATMO-ACCESS website is tracked using Matomo¹. The number of visits/page views to the VA page (<https://www.atmo-access.eu/virtual-access/>) is provided in subsection 2.1.1.
- Access to the different services through the VA portal is tracked by counting hits on the corresponding buttons.
- Effective usage of the services is recorded by each service.

¹ Matomo is an open-source web analytics tool (<https://matomo.org/>)

2.1.1. Visits to the VA portal

Tracking of visits to the VA Portal is connected to tracking of visits to the ATMO-ACCESS project webpage (<https://www.atmo-access.eu/>) itself. The visits to the VA Portal are thus shown by the metrics 'page views' and 'unique page views', where unique page views are determined by unique IP addresses.

Table 1 shows the overall page views and unique page views for 2023 until 12th of December. Figure 3 and Figure 4 show the monthly VA portal unique page views and page views, respectively. The VA portal page and the Homeless Data Portal was launched 23rd of March 2023, where the first spike in page views is shown.

Page views	1690
Unique page views	1072

Table 1: Overview of VA Portal page views and unique page views in 2023 (until 12th of December).

Figure 3: Monthly unique page views to the VA portal in 2023 (until 12th of December).

Figure 4: Monthly page views to the VA portal in 2023 (until 12th of December).

2.1.2. Access to the services from the VA portal

Access to the different services in the Virtual Access portal is tracked by counting hits on each of the buttons. Table 2 shows the button-clicks for the different services.

Footprints (all 3 services)	487
Homeless data portal	161
Timeseries analysis	131

Table 2: Clicks on the buttons for the different services.

2.2. Feedback from the general feedback form

The general feedback form for ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Services can be found here: <https://www.atmo-access.eu/virtual-access-feedback-form/> and in 10. Appendix: General Feedback Form. The form was ready in September 2023 and has been distributed in the period September to December 2023. The form has been distributed by e-mail to registered users of services and to the dedicated user panel meeting. Despite this the feedback form has only received 6 answers. Actions to promote and distribute the form further should be taken. The answers related to the Virtual Access Portal are compiled in this section, while the more specific answers applying to the different services are included in the chapters describing the feedback to these services. Figure 5 shows where the responders found out about the online services supported within the ATMO-ACCESS project. Figure 6 shows that 3 respondents accessed the Time Series Analysis service and 3 respondents accessed one of the Footprint Analysis services. Figure 7 shows an evaluation of the access to the online services from the Virtual Access Portal, where all answers are between “OK” and “Very satisfied”.

How did you find out about the online services supported within the ATMO-ACCESS project?

6 svar

Figure 5: Answers to "How did you find out about the online services supported by the ATMO-ACCESS project?". 6 answers in total.

Service accessed

6 svar

Figure 6: Answers to "Service accessed". 6 answers in total, where 3 respondents accessed footprint analysis services and 3 respondents accessed the time series analysis service.

Please evaluate the access to the online services from <https://www.atmo-access.eu/virtual-access>

Figure 7: Answers to “Please evaluate the access to the online services from <https://www.atmo-access.eu/virtual-access>”. 6 answers in total for the two first statements, 3 answers for the last statement (only asked to people accessing the footprint services).

3. ATMO-ACCESS Homeless Data Portal

The ATMO-ACCESS Homeless Data Portal (<https://homeless-data-portal.nilu.no>) is a portal for data curation of atmospheric measurement data. The portal is set up to serve scientists producing atmospheric measurements and time series resulting from research campaigns and TransNational Access (TNA) activities that have so far not been included into any data management and data curation system. These data sets are referred to as “homeless data” as they are not associated with any long-term projects nor sustainable data centres. The goal of the portal is to make more atmospheric data (collected during campaigns and via TNA) available to the end-user, as well as to provide benefits for data custodians², by tracking the access and use of their data and getting access to RI specific tools for curation.

Making the data accessible through a FAIR³ data centre is the most efficient way to ensure long-term curation and promote visibility and access to data by a large user community. This homeless data portal makes these data well documented for use and easily available.

All requests for data curation and archiving services will be handled by the relevant research infrastructures (RI), seamless for the users. The architecture of the portal is described in section 2 of deliverable [D5.1 – Detailed requirements and \(non-\) technical specifications for all services based on the user consultations](#).

The starting page of the Homeless Data Portal is shown in Figure 2.1. The user gets information about the portal and available options: 1) To request data curation and archiving, 2) to access ATMO-ACCESS related data, and 3) to request general support. Both option 1) and 3) are request forms to be filled out by the user and these requests are tracked in a redmine⁴ issue tracker by data curators.

² The individual or organization that has accountability and responsibility for the data and ensures appropriate care and maintenance of the resource.

³ Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable (<https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>)

⁴ <https://www.redmine.org/>

ATMO-ACCESS Homeless Data Portal

The Homeless data portal is a portal for data curation of atmospheric measurement data. The portal is set up to serve scientists producing atmospheric measurements and time series resulting from research campaigns and TNA activities that are normally not included into any data management and data curation system and activity. These data sets are "homeless data", not associated with any long-term projects nor sustainable data centers. The goal of the portal is to make more data available to the end-user, as well as providing benefits for data collectors in terms of usage tracking and access to RI (Research Infrastructure) specific tools for curation and data access.

All request for data curation and archiving services will be handled by a relevant research infrastructure. You must log in at the Redmine support system for ATMO-ACCESS at <https://redmine.aeris-data.fr> to see the status of your request.

Data Archiving and Curation

Apply for data curation and archiving services through the atmospheric RIs

Access Services

Data Access

Search ATMO-ACCESS related data from TNA and campaign activities

Search Data

General Support

Send a request if you have questions regarding the data in ATMO-ACCESS

Get Support

Figure 8: ATMO-ACCESS Homeless Data Portal Starting page (link: <https://homeless-data-portal.nilu.no>).

3.1. Statistics on use of the Homeless Data Portal

Statistics on the use of the Homeless Data Portal are tracked in several ways. Firstly, via the number of accesses through the ATMO-ACCESS VA Portal, then via the number of visits to the Homeless Data Portal itself (<https://homeless-data-portal.nilu.no>), and lastly via the number of requests made through the portal. The difference between accesses through the VA portal (clicks on the Homeless Data Portal button, as described in subsection 2.1.2) and visits to the web-page itself gives an indication of the number of people going directly to the webpage vs number of people routed through the VA portal. Requests in the Homeless Data Portal show

up in the issue tracker after a user requests the curation of a data set or a collection of data sets through <https://homeless-data-portal.nilu.no/request>.

3.1.1. Visits to the Homeless Data Portal

Visits to the Homeless Data Portal are tracked using Matomo. In Figure 9, a visitor map shows the distribution of visits worldwide (201 visits) and in Europe (170 visits). The visits correspond with the metrics from the VA portal where the Homeless Data Portal button had 161 clicks, showing that many users access the Homeless Data Portal through the ATMO-ACCESS VA Portal. Table 3 lists the countries with the most visits to the Homeless Data Portal, and the number of visits for each country. Several developers and curators working on the Homeless Data Portal are located in Norway and France, which is to be expected since Matomo only counts by IP addresses and does not differentiate between internal ATMO-ACCESS users and external users. Lastly Figure 10 shows the visits and actions per visit over time. Actions comprise, for instance, page views, downloads, outlinks and internal site searches.

Figure 9: Visitor map showing on the left-hand side a total of 201 visits to the Homeless Data Portal worldwide and on the right-hand side 170 visits in Europe from 23.03.2023 - 31.12.2023.

COUNTRY	VISITS
Norway	38
France	26
United States	21
Spain	19
Greece	16
Netherlands	12
Finland	11
Italy	9
Sweden	8
Germany	7

Table 3: Countries with the most visits to the Homeless Data Portal from 23.03.2023 - 31.12.2023.

Figure 10: Two graphs showing visits and actions per visit over time from 23.03.2023 - 31.12.2023. The upper graph shows both number of visits (in blue) and actions per visit (in orange), while the lower graph shows only actions per visit to properly see the scale. This gives an average of 2.3 actions (page views, downloads, outlinks and internal site searches) per visit.

3.1.2. Requests through the Homeless Data Portal

Requests in the Homeless Data Portal show up in a redmine issue tracker after a user requests the curation of a data set or a collection of data sets through <https://homeless-data-portal.nilu.no/request>. After a request shows up in the issue tracker, the data curators decide on which RI the data set(s) are compatible with, and the data set(s) follow the normal data

curation process. Statistics on the requests can be found in Table 4. The table counts the total number of requests, the number of unique requests (some have sent similar requests two times for the same set of data), and open and closed issues. Open issues are usually because only parts of a collection of data sets have been sent to the RI and curated. This is shown in the difference between “Number of requested data curation services” and “Number of datasets curated”. Lastly, the Table 4 lists the project associations that have requested curation services and the RIs their request have been associated with.

Number of requests (unique)	11 (8)
Open issues in progress	5
Closed issues (unique)	6 (3)
Number of requested data curation services	> 154
Number of datasets curated	125
Project associations	2 (ATMO-ACCESS TNA, RI-URBANS)
Number of requests associated with ACTRIS DC	11
Number of requests associated with IAGOS DC	0
Number of requests associated with ICOS DC	0

Table 4: Statistics on requests through the Homeless Data Portal from launch to 06.12.2023.

3.2. Feedback from users on the Homeless Data Portal

Feedback on the service is provided in several ways:

- Through user panel meetings
- Internal feedback

The end of the feedback period was in December 2023, and suggestions and most feedback will be taken into account during January 2024. Furthermore, homeless data owners were encouraged to fill in the general feedback form but to date no answer directly related to the Homeless Data Portal has been received.

3.2.1. User panel for Homeless Data Portal

User panels consist of meetings with a small group of hand-picked people within the RIs that comment on the service. The first feedback meeting with the User Panel of the Homeless Data Portal took place in May 2022.

Participants: Christoph Gerbig (IAGOS/ICOS), Wahid Mellouki (ACTRIS), Eleni Marinou, Jean-Philippe Putaud (not able to attend).

The User Panel made the following recommendations and comments as regards to the Homeless Data Portal, as gathered in the sentences below:

- It could be a useful tool if there is a new instrument or methodology that is not accommodated for by one of the RIs.
- All these requests will have to be handled manually.
- The User panel thinks that the overall concept could be very useful, but would depend on who will have access to the data curation services.
- We, the user panel, should encourage homeless data owners to request curation and archiving of the data that is in the perimeter of the atmospheric RIs.
- The User panel does not consider data that will be collected by the campaigns in the atmo-access project as "homeless data" as these belongs to projects. However, in ATMO-ACCESS these data fulfill the criteria as homeless as projects are not sustainable data archiving systems.
- A tool that will check data directly on upload would be useful, e.g. that it follows the correct format (like the CF format checker) - could also be a link to data submission and tools used in EVDC- ESA Validation Data Center (at least for aerosol remote sensing part).
- This tool could be relevant for high resolution ozone sonde data/radiosonde data
- The user panel is a bit unclear what could be categorized as homeless data, and to what extend the tool will offer resources to help curated large datasets that are not accommodated elsewhere.
- The user panel thinks that the "concept" of the homeless data portal is a great idea.
- The user panel thinks that the application can be widely used by the community, but it depends on how well the information about the service is spread. There is a need, but to get people to apply requires them to understand what kind of support they can expect.
- Within the GHG community there is a regular collection of GHG data from sites that are not part of ICOS, these sites could be typical users of the homeless data portal.

3.2.2. Internal feedback on the Homeless Data Portal

Internal feedback includes propositions of improvement from the internal ATMO-ACCESS virtual access team and was collected at the end of the first feedback period.

Participants: Cathrine Lund Myhre, Lise Eder Murberg, Yong Lin

- Data Access/Search Data functionality does not work for its intended purpose. Right now, the links direct the user to the full data catalogues of ACTRIS, ICOS and IAGOS, but the service should give the user direct access to datasets curated through the ATMO-ACCESS project.
- The Redmine Issue Tracker is not great for tracking correspondence between users and curators, as users do not have easy access to the tracker. Therefore, much of the communication goes through e-mail to help users formatting their data.
- Great tool but needs to be promoted more to all relevant users.

4. Time Series Analysis

The Time Series Analysis service provides users a tool to identify, use and combine data across RIs and data repositories. It aims at serving a large variety of users (students, academics, private or public organizations, NGOs, communities of projects, etc...) by providing a dedicated Virtual Research Environment (VRE) for facilitating their exploration of multiple in situ datasets with long time series of different variables. The service makes accessible the most commonly used basic metrics (e.g. means, percentiles) and statistical analysis (e.g. trends), as well as visualization tools to look at e.g. 2D or 3D scatter plots. The combination of different variables important for climate and air quality recorded by ACTRIS, IAGOS and ICOS allows users to explore relevant cross-cutting issues. An example of the search functionality for available variables of the Time Series Analysis service is shown in Figure 11.

The architecture of the service is described in section 4 of deliverable [D5.1 – Detailed requirements and \(non-\) technical specifications for all services based on the user consultations](#).

Time-series analysis

Figure 11: ATMO-ACCESS Time Series Analysis Search datasets page (link: <https://permalink.aeris-data.fr/atmo-access-timeseries>).

4.1. Statistics on use of the Time Series Analysis service

Statistics on the use of the Time Series Analysis are tracked in several ways. Firstly, via the number of accesses through the ATMO-ACCESS VA Portal, then via the number of visits to the Time-series analysis web-service itself, and lastly via the number of requests through the service. The difference between accesses through the VA portal (clicks on the “Tools for analyzing time series” button, as described in subsection 2.1.2) and visits to the web-page itself gives an indication of the number of people going directly to the webpage vs number of people routed through the VA portal. Each RI provides access to their datasets through a dedicated API that is requested by the service. The number of requests to the service is considered similar to the number of datasets accessed through the RIs data access APIs⁵. This means the number of datasets accessed in step “3. Select datasets” in the service, which is the step after “2. Search dataset” which is shown in Figure 11. The statistics are available since June 2023.

4.1.1. Number of visits to the Time Series Analysis service

Visits to the Time Series Analysis give an indication about how many people are using the service. Figure 12 shows the number of unique visits over time. The total number of unique visits is 128 for the period June 22, 2023 to November 30, 2023, where the high peak at around 26th of September most likely is when the first user panel was held. Unique visits refer to visits made by unique IP addresses.

⁵ An application programming interface (API) is a way for two or more computer programs to communicate with each other. It is a type of software interface, offering a service to other pieces of software.

Time series service - Visits

Figure 12: Number of unique visits over time – Time series service from June 22, 2023 to November 30, 2023.

4.1.2. Number of requests through Time Series Analysis Service

The number of requests is the number of datasets accessed through the RIs data access APIs. This means the number of datasets accessed in step “3. Select datasets” in the service. Figure 13 shows the number of requests over time. The total number of requests for the time series service is 540 for the period June 22, 2023 to November 30, 2023. On average, 4.2 datasets were requested by each visit.

Time series service - Requests

Figure 13: Number of requests over time – Time series service from June 22, 2023 to November 30, 2023.

4.2. Feedback from users on the Time Series Analysis service

Feedback on the service is provided in two ways:

- Through user's panel meeting every six months
- Through the general feedback form

The end of the feedback period was in December 2023, and suggestions and most feedback will be taken into account during January 2024.

4.2.1. User panel for Time Series Analysis service

The first Feedback meeting with the User Panel of the time-series analysis service took place in September 2023. General feedback was very positive about the main features of the service (filtering and analysis). The major remark was on the need to improve the documentation and

the help for the users. Other remarks were about how to improve the ergonomics of the service and minor features that were missing.

More details on the feedback are available in Milestone MS5.4 section 2: <https://wp1.aeris-data.fr/wp-content-aeris/uploads/sites/82/2023/11/atmo-access-milestone-20-v2.1.pdf>

4.2.2. Feedback form for the Time Series Analysis service

Three users of the time series analysis service have provided feedback via the form. Figure 14 shows the results of their evaluation of the different aspects of the service: i) information about the service offered, ii) interaction with and support by the VA service providers, iii) interpretation and understanding of the outcome and results, and iv) compliance of the service with the user expectations. All aspects of the service have gotten “Satisfied” or “Vary satisfied”. Furthermore, an overall rating of the service from 1-5 is given in Figure 15, giving an average score of 4.7. Lastly, Figure 16 shows the rating given by the users with respect to the benefits of the time series analysis service.

Please evaluate the the online service you have used

Figure 14: Evaluation of different aspects of the time series analysis.

Please evaluate the service provided by the ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Access activity, from your perspective

Figure 15: The number of user responses vs their numbered evaluation of the time series analysis, where 1 is the lowest and 5 is the highest score.

Shortly comment the benefits of the Virtual Access and/or lessons learnt

Figure 16: The number of user responses vs the benefits of the time series analysis as seen by the respondents.

Further comments/suggestions given by the users:

- "Thank you! keep going."
- "The system has very nice functionalities. If we can download the final data that are being used for the graphics that would be great (I understand that will be implemented). If possible, BL/MT/UT meteo data in the case of IAGOS would also be very valuable (for the moment only O3 and CO are available). Have you thought about using near-surface air quality data (e.g. O3, PM, etc) from EMEP or other networks? Honestly, I am not sure I will use it very regularly for my work, because I am involved in other types of projects at the moment. However, I think it will be very useful to produce plots that I can show in some lectures or for some of the students working on their Bachelor or even MSc theses."

5. Footprint analysis service (ACTRIS)

The ACTRIS footprint analysis service provides model tools to users for the interpretation of ground-based aerosol and trace gas observations. The users can request model runs to produce data products (e.g., footprints, source contributions) for defined ground-based stations and products or search and use data products for existing locations. Footprint products are used to provide air mass origin information that helps understand the trajectory of the air masses and to analyze atmospheric observations. Source contribution products give modelled contributions to a variable from a given sector e.g., modelled contribution to surface black carbon (BC) from residential and commercial sector. All products are generated using the FLEXPART (FLEXible PARTicle dispersion model) and include footprint analysis for air masses arriving at the station on a 3-hour time resolution for 20 days back in time, except for near-real-time (NRT) products which are for the last 3 days and include a 1-day forecast. Currently data products can be requested for the variables and categories described in Table 5.

Black carbon	Standard products for analyzing black carbon (BC) measurements at sites with long time series
Dust	Products for analyzing dust events at various sites
Specialized black carbon	Tailored products for analyzing black carbon (BC) measurements from specific campaigns
Other	Tailored products for analyzing land-use change, sulfate, CO and OC from specific campaigns
Microplastic	Tailored products for analyzing microplastic (MP) measurements from specific campaigns
Near Real Time (NRT)	Footprint products to be used for analyzing NRT data and 1 day forecast

Table 5: Current FLEXPART products available for ground-based aerosol and trace gas observations.

The starting page of the ACTRIS Footprint analysis service is shown in Figure 17. A user of this service has different options: i) to request new model runs, ii) to access current products already produced within ATMO-ACCESS, and iii) to get general support, e.g., for in-depth interpretation. “Available FLEXPART Footprint products” shows ACTRIS stations with available standard black carbon footprint and source contribution products for years between 2012-2022. The “FLEXPART Station map” shows a map of all stations with available products, where the marker for each station is dependent on the categories in Table 5.

ATMO-ACCESS

FLEXPART products for ground based aerosol and trace gas observations

Landing page for the ATMO-ACCESS FLEXPART products.

FLEXPART Model Run

Request access to FLEXPART model run

Request Access

FLEXPART Products and Information

Access FLEXPART products and descriptions

Access Data

General Support

Do you have questions regarding the FLEXPART products in ATMO-ACCESS?

Get Support

Available FLEXPART Footprint products

FLEXPART coverage (Click the rectangle to access the data)

FLEXPART Station Map

Figure 17: Starting page for ATMO-ACCESS Footprint products for ground-based aerosol and trace gas observations (link: <https://flexpart-request.nilu.no/>).

5.1. Statistics on use of the ACTRIS footprint analysis service

Statistics on the use of the footprint analysis service are tracked in several ways. First it is the number of accesses through the ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Access Portal, then the number of visits to the ACTRIS footprint analysis service itself (<https://flexpart-request.nilu.no/>) and lastly the number of FLEXPART requests, i.e. the request forms filled out with request for model runs at a given station/location.

5.1.1. Visits to the web interface

Visits to the ACTRIS footprint analysis service web-page is tracked using matomo. The visitor map in Figure 18 shows the distribution of visits worldwide (565 visits) and in Europe (478 visits). Table 6 lists the countries with the most visits to the ACTRIS footprint analysis service web-page, and the number of visits made by each country. Lastly, Figure 19 shows the visits and actions (e.g., page views, downloads, outlinks and internal site searches) per visit over time.

Figure 18: Visitor map showing on the left-hand side a total of 565 visits to the ACTRIS Footprint Analysis Service web-page worldwide, and on the right-hand side 478 visits in Europe during 15.05.2023 - 31.12.2023.

COUNTRY	VISITS
Norway	175
United States	73
Switzerland	45
France	37
Spain	32
Greece	31
Italy	29
United Kingdom	28
Germany	25
Finland	22

Table 6: Countries with the most visits to the ACTRIS footprint analysis service web-page during 15.05.2023 - 31.12.2023.

Figure 19: Two graphs showing visits and actions per visit over time from 15.05.2023 - 31.12.2023. The upper graph shows both number of visits (in blue) and actions per visit (in orange), while the lower graph shows only actions per visit to properly see the scale. This gives an average of 2.4 actions (page views, downloads, outlinks and internal site searches) per visit.

5.1.2. Request for service

The number of requests for the footprint analysis service is tracked in the Aeris Redmine issue tracker. Statistics on the requests can be found in Table 7. The ACTRIS footprint service started out with black carbon (BC) products, and has extended with other products such as dust, microplastics, NRT and more (other products) since the launch of the service. As this service is

new within this project, many ACTRIS sites have asked for the standardized products such as BC and NRT which can explain the high demand.

Statistic	Number
Requests	34
Requests in progress	1
Completed issues	33
Stations with black carbon products for 10 years, 3h resolution (years 2012-2022)	21
Stations with dust products	6
Stations with specialized black carbon products	14
Stations with other products	3
Stations with microplastics products	6
Stations with NRT products	24

Table 7: Statistics on requests of the service via the FLEXPART request form on the ACTRIS footprint analysis service web-page until 06.12.2023.

5.2. Feedback from users on the ACTRIS footprint analysis service

Feedback on the service is provided in several ways:

- Through user's panel meeting every six months
- Internal feedback
- Through the general feedback form

The end of the feedback period was in December 2023, and suggestions and most feedback will be taken into account during January 2024.

5.2.1. User panel on the ACTRIS footprint analysis service

The first Feedback meeting with the User Panel of the footprint service took place in September 2023. In general, the user panel was impressed with the number of footprints and data products available. Some comments on downloading data where one user wish to view data without downloading a file and several users wished for batch download of files or a simple API for machine-to-machine download. Lastly, the users wished for more documentation on the available products, better labeled stations and possibly a simple training video. The details of the responses are summarized in Milestone MS5.4 section 1.1: <https://wp1.aeris-data.fr/wp-content-aeris/uploads/sites/82/2023/11/atmo-access-milestone-20-v2.1.pdf>

5.2.2. Internal feedback on ACTRIS footprint analysis service

Internal feedback includes suggestions for improvement from the internal ATMO-ACCESS team and was collected at the end of the first feedback period.

Participants: Cathrine Lund Myhre, Lise Eder Murberg, Sabine Eckhardt, Nikolaos Evangeliou, Richard Rud, Tove Svendby, Wenche Aas

The main comments are listed below:

- There are many requests for products other than BC in the portal. It is not clear in the portal that there are several different products and this should be cleaned up and explained better.
- What is the difference between BC and BC (ACTRIS)? Standard and specialized?
- The documentation should be improved. It is only available for BC right now.
- Make better legends at the maps, and include all products offered.
- When going into the maps/products we lose control over which station it is.
- Include VOC NRT footprint as a product?
- EBAS ID codes are not easy to understand for users.

5.2.3. Response on feedback form related to ACTRIS footprint analysis.

The general feedback form received only one response related to the ACTRIS footprint analysis service, and the corresponding answer can be seen in Table 8.

Please evaluate the online service you have used	
Information about the service offered	Poor
Interaction with and support by the virtual access service provider(s) (scientific and technical support)	Very satisfied
Interpretation and understanding of the outcome and results	Poor
Did the service comply with your expectations?	OK
Please evaluate the service provided by the ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Access activity, from your perspective (where 1 is the lowest and 5 is the highest score)	3
Shortly comment the benefits of the Virtual Access and/or lessons learnt	Scientific and technical support, Ready-to-use graphics
Lastly, do you have any further comments/suggestions for improvement?	The service was ok, but I think it could be improved.

Table 8: Answer to the general feedback form on the ACTRIS footprint analysis service.

6. Footprint analysis service (ICOS)

The ICOS STILT station footprint calculation and viewing service allows users to explore greenhouse gas concentrations and footprints for ground-based stations in Europe.

The STILT results viewer (Figure 20) allows to select all available footprint data at the repository and to display an animation of the footprints together with the modelled concentrations and contributions from different source categories. For ICOS stations, also the measured concentrations are included for comparison. The viewer also provides the option to download the model results.

The STILT calculation service allows users to start new STILT model runs for any new location within the model domain (Figure 21).

STILT results viewer

[Download results](#) [Re-package results](#) [Help](#)

Legal mentions

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Figure 20: ATMO-ACCESS ICOS STILT results viewer page (link: <https://stilt.icos-cp.eu/viewer/>).

STILT calculation service Job starter

Help

Existing STILT footprints

Select station here or on the map

Create new STILT footprint

Latitude (decimal degree)

Longitude (decimal degree)

Altitude above ground (meters)

Site id (usually a 3 letter code)

Load data

Start date (YYYY-MM-DD)

End date (YYYY-MM-DD)

Submit STILT job

Submitted STILT jobs

Show details

Finished computations

- ★ Site 'PTZ800' (2022-11-01 - 2022-12-31)
- ★ Site 'ADE050' (2022-01-01 - 2022-12-31)
- ★ Site 'GIO020' (2021-01-01 - 2021-12-31)
- ★ Site 'ACQ020' (2020-01-01 - 2020-12-31)
- ★ Site 'POS025' (2020-01-01 - 2020-12-31)
- ★ Site 'ADE020' (2020-01-01 - 2020-12-31)
- ★ Site 'MAI810' (2020-01-01 - 2020-12-31)
- ★ Site 'MAI810' (2022-01-01 - 2022-12-31)
- ★ Site 'ACQ020' (2022-01-01 - 2022-12-31)
- ★ Site 'POS025' (2022-01-01 - 2022-12-31)
- ★ Site 'GIO020' (2022-01-01 - 2022-12-31)
- ★ Site 'GIO020' (2022-01-01 - 2022-12-31)
- ★ Site 'ADE020' (2022-01-01 - 2022-12-31)
- ★ Site 'GLC100' (2021-01-12 - 2022-12-17)

Legal mentions

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Figure 21: ATMO-ACCESS ICOS STILT calculation service page (link: <https://stilt.icos-cp.eu/worker/>).

6.1. Statistics on use of the ICOS footprint analysis service

Statistics on the use of the ICOS STILT station footprint calculation and viewing service are tracked through the ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Access Portal, recording the number of model runs started and result packages downloaded. The number of times the footprint animation was viewed on the ICOS STILT results viewer page is not tracked separately, this will be added in the next release together with the added functionality for CH₄.

The statistics are available since June 2023.

6.1.1. Model runs started

Figure 22 shows the number of model runs started since June 2023. Each model run applies to a single station, the requested time period can vary between a few days and several years (up to 17 years). Note that in autumn, specific users started a large number of model runs for use in their projects.

Figure 22: Number of STILT model runs started in the ICOS footprint service between June 24, 2023 and December 8, 2023. The upper graph shows model run starts per day and the lower graph shows the cumulative sum of runs with a total of 702 runs.

As each run can cover one or more days of footprints we can also look at the number of footprint days. Each day calculated will produce eight 3-hourly footprints

Figure 23 The monthly number of footprint days calculated in the GHG footprint tool

Over the period in total 36 users requested in 730 requests calculation of 118 881 footprint days, which corresponds to in total 951 048 calculated footprints.

6.1.2. Model results downloaded

Figure 24 shows the number of model result packages downloaded since June 2023. Each packages contains footprints and concentration time series for a single station and one year.

Figure 24: Number of downloads of packaged model results in the ICOS footprint service between June 14, 2023 and December 8, 2023. The upper graph shows downloads per day and the lower graph shows the cumulative sum of package downloads with a total of 58 download.

As each download can cover one or more days of footprints we can also look at the number of footprint days downloaded. Each day in the download archive will consist of eight 3-hourly footprints

Figure 25 The monthly number of footprint days downloaded from the GHG footprint tool

Over the period in total 31 individual users requested through 76 download requests 63 471 footprint days, which corresponds to in total 509 928 footprints.

6.2. Feedback from users on the ICOS footprint analysis

Feedback on the service is provided in several ways:

- Through user's panel meeting every six months
- Through the general feedback form

The end of the feedback period was in December 2023 and suggestions and most feedback will be taken into account until January 2024.

6.2.1. User panel on the ICOS footprint analysis

The first feedback meeting with the User Panel of the footprint service took place in September 2023. In the meeting users gave valuable feedback on improvements to the missing navigation links between the viewer and the calculation tool. Also a valid remark was made that other users email addresses should not be visible in the calculation queue. Due to the large number of requests the map with available data is getting cluttered so suggested was to be able to select subsets of the viewed set of stations for example based on the length of the available time series, whether observations are available, type of station (mountain/surface) and ICOS/non-ICOS station.

Detail of the feedback is available in Milestone MS5.4 section 1.1: <https://wp1.aeris-data.fr/wp-content-aeris/uploads/sites/82/2023/11/atmo-access-milestone-20-v2.1.pdf>

6.2.2. Response on feedback form related to ICOS footprint analysis

The general feedback form received only one response related to the ICOS footprint analysis service, and the corresponding answer can be seen in Table 9.

Please evaluate the online service you have used	
Information about the service offered	Satisfied
Interaction with and support by the virtual access service provider(s) (scientific and technical support)	Very satisfied
Interpretation and understanding of the outcome and results	Satisfied
Did the service comply with your expectations?	Very satisfied
Please evaluate the service provided by the ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Access activity, from your perspective	5
Shortly comment the benefits of the Virtual Access and/or lessons learnt	Saving time, easy data access, Immediate access to the results / interactive analysis
Lastly, do you have any further comments/suggestions for improvement?	1. Adding a measure of uncertainty to the footprint results would be useful. For each footprint, one could possibly make a corresponding map containing confidence intervals by bootstrapping the particle

	<p>release data, though this might be computationally intensive.</p> <p>2. Might be useful to have some guidance on lower height limits when specifying new stations. At 100 m, the influence of local sources / sub-grid scale variation is fairly small, but at 2 m this is quite high (and depends on the gas considered). Some indication of what might be reasonable could be useful.</p>
--	--

Table 9: Answer to the general feedback form on the ICOS footprint service.

7. Footprint analysis service (IAGOS)

The IAGOS footprint analysis service combines the viewer of FLEXPART footprints and modelled SOFT-IO CO₂ contributions and allows users to explore tropospheric vertical profiles of carbon monoxide mixing ratios (measured by IAGOS) in conjunction with source attribution data (calculated using the SOFT-IO model). The vertical profiles are from airports visited by commercial aircrafts equipped with IAGOS' instrumentation. The SOFT-IO model is based on the coupling of FLEXPART backward footprint (with the receptor points located along the profile) with emission inventory databases. The service provides a visualization of the above-mentioned data via a simple, attractive user interface. Figure 26 shows the IAGOS footprints viewer page where users can select an airport and a date to visualize the footprints.

⁶ Source attribution using FlexparT and carbon monoxide emission inventories for In-situ Observation database, cf. Sauvage et al., 2017, doi.org/10.5194/acp-17-15271-2017

Figure 26: ATMO-ACCESS IAGOS footprints viewer Starting page (link: <https://permalink.aeris-data.fr/atmo-access-footprint>).

7.1. Statistics on use of the IAGOS footprint analysis service

Statistics on the use of the IAGOS footprint analysis service are tracked in several ways. Firstly, via the number of accesses through the ATMO-ACCESS VA Portal, then via the number of visits to the IAGOS footprint analysis web-service itself, and lastly via the number of requests through the service. The difference between accesses through the VA portal (clicks on the button, as described in subsection 2.1.2) and visits to the web-page itself gives an indication of the number

of people going directly to the webpage vs number of people routed through the VA portal. The statistics are available since June 2023.

7.1.1. Number of visits

Visits to the Time Series Analysis give an indication about how many people are using the service. Figure 27 shows the number of unique (one user per day) visits over time. The total number of unique visits is 118 for the period June 22, 2023 to November 30, 2023.

Footprints service - Visits

Figure 27: Number of visits over time - IAGOS Footprints viewer service from June 22, 2023 to November 30, 2023.

7.1.2. Number of requests

The number of requests is the number of footprints displayed. Figure 28 shows the number of requests over time.

Footprints service - Requests

Figure 28: Number of requests over time – IAGOS Footprints viewer service from June 22, 2023, to November 30, 2023.

The total number of requests for the IAGOS footprints viewer is 2603 for the period June 22, 2023, to November 30, 2023.

7.2. Feedback from users on the IAGOS footprint analysis service

Feedback on the service is provided in two ways:

- Through user's panel meeting every six months
- Through the general feedback form

7.2.1. User panel on the IAGOS footprint analysis

The first Feedback meeting with the User Panel of the footprint service took place in September 2023. General feedback was very positive about the main features of the. The main feedback was on the need to improve the documentation and the help for the users. Other remarks were about how to improve the service by adding additional search criteria and plotting additional observational data.

More details on the feedback are available in Milestone MS5.4 section 1.2: <https://wp1.aeris-data.fr/wp-content-aeris/uploads/sites/82/2023/11/atmo-access-milestone-20-v2.1.pdf>

7.2.2. Response on feedback form related to IAGOS footprint analysis

The general feedback form received only one response related to the IAGOS footprint analysis service, and the corresponding answer can be seen in Table 10.

Please evaluate the online service you have used	
Information about the service offered	Satisfied
Interaction with and support by the virtual access service provider(s) (scientific and technical support)	Very satisfied
Interpretation and understanding of the outcome and results	Satisfied
Did the service comply with your expectations?	Satisfied
Please evaluate the service provided by the ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Access activity, from your perspective	4
Shortly comment the benefits of the Virtual Access and/or lessons learnt	Saving time, scientific and technical support, ready-to-use graphics
Lastly, do you have any further comments/suggestions for improvement?	n/a

Table 10: Answer to the general feedback form on the IAGOS footprint service

8. Discussion and next steps

User statistics show that most users access the services through the ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Access Portal. There is generally good satisfaction with the VA portal. The Homeless Data portal has few, but extensive requests (several datasets/variables per request). It is a good concept and will be promoted more to the community. The Time-series analysis has 128 visits, and most requests happen through the data access API (540 requests). Results from the feedback show overall satisfaction of the tool. Suggestions from the user panel to improve technical issues will be taken into account. The footprint services are generally in high demand, as indicated by the user statistics, and the overall feedback from the user panels is very positive. For the ACTRIS footprint service, most feedback refers to a lack of documentation and suggests some technical improvements. This particular feedback has already been taken into account and the service has been updated. For the ICOS and IAGOS footprint service, feedback relates to some technical improvements and suggestions to include uncertainties for both, and also to include methane as a variable in the ICOS footprint analysis. This will be evaluated and included in January 2024.

This report will be used for refinement for improved services, and the evaluation and upgrades will happen by the end of January 2024. Furthermore, the statistics in the report indicates if any more promotion of the services is needed, and if that's the case this will be planned for early 2024. The next report on feedback will include a chapter on what updates are done after this report and how the feedback was evaluated.

9. Conclusion

This deliverable concludes the first feedback period. The feedback received will be evaluated by the respective teams and taken into account by the end of January 2024.

10. Appendix: General Feedback Form

Feedback questionnaire for users of ATMO-ACCESS online services

You have used free services available from this site: <https://www.atmo-access.eu/virtual-access>. To keep them free for you, ATMO-ACCESS deeply values feedback from users. We hope you will spend a few minutes on this feedback schema to feed our requested usage monitoring.

Your opinions and feedback will help the ATMO-ACCESS team to understand what we're doing well and where we need to get better. The feedback will be used by the VA management and development team, in strategic decision and project coordination.

* indicates that the question is mandatory

1. Email address *

2. Privacy notice *

The ATMO-ACCESS privacy notice can be accessed at this link:
<https://www.atmo-access.eu/atmo-access-privacy-policy/>

All replies will be treated in the strictest confidence. The information given will only be used for monitoring and assessment purposes in accordance with the European [General Data Protection Regulation](#).

Tick all that applies

I agree with the ATMO-ACCESS privacy policy and terms of use

3. First name

4. Last name

5. Do you agree to be contacted for further feedback or to be informed of further improvements? *

Tick all that applies

- Yes
 No

6. Home institution

7. Your background and position *

Check all that apply.

Tick all that applies

- Academic (post-doc, researcher, lecturer)
 Student (undergraduate, PhD)
 Project leader
 Air quality network and/or other Research Infrastructure
 Industry
 Private enterprise
 Government Organisation
 Independent Scientist
 Andre: _____

8. How did you find out about the online services supported within the ATMO-ACCESS project? *

Tick all that applies

- ATMO-ACCESS website
- Research infrastructure websites
- Direct mailing from Research Infrastructure
- Twitter
- LinkedIn
- Other social media
- Information received by colleagues/personal contacts
- Information received at event
- Andre: _____

9. Service accessed *

Mark only one oval.

- Homeless Data Portal Jump to question 12
- Footprint Analysis Jump to question 10
- Time Series Analysis Jump to question 12
- MOOC - Massive Open Online Courses Jump to question 12
- Helpdesk for any of the services Jump to question 12

10. Footprint Analysis Service accessed *

Mark only one oval.

- Greenhouse gasses
- Tropospheric vertical gradients
- Aerosol distribution and source analysis

11. Please evaluate the access to the online services from <https://www.atmo-access.eu/virtual-access>

*

Mark only one oval per row

	Not relevant	Poor	OK	Satisfied	Very satisfied
Publicity and information on the access portal before login	<input type="radio"/>				
System for registration and authentication to get access to the service	<input type="radio"/>				
Publicity and information on the access portal after login	<input type="radio"/>				

Jump to question 13

12. Please evaluate the access to the online services from <https://www.atmo-access.eu/virtual-access>

*

Mark only one oval per row

	Not relevant	Poor	OK	Satisfied	Very satisfied
Publicity and information on the access portal before login	<input type="radio"/>				
System for registration and authentication to get access to the service	<input type="radio"/>				

Jump to question 13

13. Please evaluate the the online service you have used *

Mark only one oval per row

	Not relevant	Poor	OK	Satisfied	Very satisfied
Information about the service offered	<input type="radio"/>				
Interaction with and support by the virtual access service provider(s) (scientific and technical support)	<input type="radio"/>				
Interpretation and understanding of the outcome and results	<input type="radio"/>				
Did the service comply with your expectations?	<input type="radio"/>				

14. Please evaluate the service provided by the ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Access activity, from your perspective *
This covers both the access process and the online services

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Very poor Excellent

15. If your evaluation is ≤ 2 , we appreciate if you can briefly explain why:

16. Shortly comment the benefits of the Virtual Access and/or lessons learnt

Tick all that apply

- Saving time
 Scientific and technical support
 Easy data access
 Immediate access to the results / interactive analysis
 Ready-to-use graphics
 Andre: _____

17. Lastly, do you have any further comments/suggestions for improvement?

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